

The expansion of Russian wheat land suitability in response to climate change

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ABSTRACT

We provided an examination of the past-to-future thermal suitability for winter wheat cultivation over Russia to better understand how the increasing warming is affecting the Russian wheat sector and discuss some realistic opportunities. The analyses were carried out by means of a multi-model ensemble analysis from the most updated bias-corrected outputs from five CMIP5 Earth System Models (1951-2099) under two representative concentration pathways (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5), and the Era-Interim dataset (1979-2016).

We found an average increase of thermal suitability of 10 Mha per decade over the past 30 years, consistently with the observed switch from spring to the higher yielding winter. An increase of thermal suitability toward the north-western regions and in the Far East also resulted from future projections. Conversely, an increasing risk of extreme heat events is expected to occur in the southern regions of Russia, which currently represent the most productive and intensively managed wheat cultivation area. We discussed in deep some adaptation strategies able both to take advantage of the agricultural expansion and to face the increasing temperature extremes, such as the agricultural land recovery, identification of the optimal sowing period, crop and variety switching.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wheat currently represents the most economically and culturally valuable crop for Russia which ranks between among the world's first producers (~50 Mt per year averaged over the period 1993-2013, data from FAOSTAT database (FAO, 2017)). According to the Foreign Agricultural Service of the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA, 2017) and the International Grains Council expectations (IGC, 2017), in 2016 Russia exported 30 Mt of wheat, becoming the first global wheat exporter. The primacy of Russian wheat exports could be increasingly important for both the world agriculture (e.g. to meet the growing food demand) and the country's economy, recently also aimed to improve the domestic agriculture as a response to the Western economic sanctions (Liefert and Liefert, 2017; Bond et al., 2015).

The recent increase in Russian wheat production was already deeply discussed (Liefert and Liefert, 2017; Liefert et al., 2010) and explained mainly by the collapse of the livestock sectors after the Soviet-era and by the increase in wheat yields thanks to plentiful investments from a new class of large, vertically integrated enterprises that combine primary agriculture, processing, distribution and sometimes retail sale (Liefert et al., 2010). Both these factors were a consequence of the transition toward a more market-oriented land-use planning economy occurred after the collapse of the former Soviet Union (Liefert and Liefert, 2017).

Recent works suggested that the Russian agricultural sector is also likely affected by the global warming, which is shifting the areas bio-climatically suitable for agriculture to the northern latitudes by removing the cold-temperature constraints (Zabel et al., 2014; Ramankutty et al., 2002), and increasing the frequency of heat waves and warm spells in the southern regions (Perkins et al., 2012), where most of the grain production currently takes place (Asseng, 2014; Teixeira et al., 2013).

Indeed, projected land suitability over Russian Federation was already presented within global assessments (Zabel et al., 2014, Zhang and Cai, 2011; Ramankutty et al., 2002) and by regional assessments accounting only for European Russia (Schierhorn et al., 2014), or not accounting for extreme events (Sirotenko et al., 2007). However, an updated regional evaluation that considers both the long-term trends and the extreme events, and that embrace also the Ural, Siberia and Far East regions, is still lacking. Moreover, a closer look at the recent warming changes (also lacking) could help to reveal some realistic opportunities, as for instance the recovery of the abandoned croplands that occurred the European Russia (Schierhorn et al., 2013).

Here we aimed to investigate how the global warming is likely affecting the thermal suitability for winter wheat in Russia and, in turns, identify the best management strategies to support the wheat sector. Thus, we made a simple yet informative screening on the past-to-future thermal condition for winter wheat development (*Triticum aestivum*, L. 1753) over the Russian Federation by looking at the fulfillment of wheat heat requirement and the occurrences of stressful heat and frost extreme events. The analyses were carried out over both the recent past and future projections by means of a multi model ensemble analysis from the most updated bias-corrected outputs from five CMIP5 Earth System Models (ESMs, Tab.1) under two representative concentration pathways (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5) and the Era-Interim dataset (Tab. 1).

Total amounts and geographical distributions of croplands plus grassland embracing suitable thermal conditions for wheat cultivation are shown and discussed with the recent trends of wheat yields and harvested area. Some realistic opportunities and possible adaptation strategies are discussed.

2 METHODS

2.1 *Wheat heat requirement (Growing Degree Days)*

A large number of crop models predict plant development by means of the degree days (DD) algorithm (Weir et al., 1984; McMaster et al., 1991; Jamieson et al., 1998; Ritchie and Nesmith, 1991), which gives the timing of crop phenological development. According to its simplest formulation, the DD algorithm totalizes average daily air temperatures above a given temperature threshold (hereinafter *base temperature*, T_0), until a phase is completed (Wang, 1960; Ritchie and Nesmith, 1991). The totalized amount, expressed as growing degree days (GDD), is assumed as an intrinsic characteristic of the crop phase (Wang, 1960, Davidson and Campbell, 1983). The underlying assumption of the DD algorithm is that the rate of crop development (i.e. the reciprocal of the time to mature a given phase, d^{-1}) is a linear function of daily air temperature (Davidson and Campbell, 1983), formally expressed as:

$$Dr = a + b \cdot T \quad (1)$$

Where Dr is the developmental rate [d^{-1}], a and b are empirical coefficients of the linear function, and T is the daily average air temperature [$^{\circ}C$]. The intercept of the linear regression with the axis of temperature ($-a/b$) provided the best estimate for the base temperature ($T_0, ^{\circ}C$), while the reciprocal of the slopes (i.e. $1/b$) equals to the crop heat requirement expressed as growing degree days (GDD, $^{\circ}Cd$).

By means of phenological observations (a phase time length and related average air temperature experienced during that phase) it is possible to verify whether a phase developmental rate is a linear function of daily air temperature and, if so, estimate reliable values for GDD and T_0

To our purposes, we used field observations (Figure S1) on wheat development and corresponding temperature measurement from the work of Podolsky (1984). Data involved four wheat cultivars (Iroda, Kharkovskaya 46, Surkhak 5688 and Shark) collected in different regions of Russian Federation, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Tadzhikistan (former USSR).

Observed wheat phenological phases from Podolsky (1984) were: 1) from *sowing to full mass sprouting*; 2) from *full mass sprouting to the beginning of tillering*, 3) from *beginning of tillering to full stalk shooting*, 4) from *full stalk shooting to heading*; 5) from *heading to wax ripeness*. Albeit phenological observations from Podolsky (1984) do not follow any widely-established phenological scale (e.g. Zadoks (Zadoks et al., 1974), Freekes (Large, 1954)) they have the advantage of being well contextualized for the study domain (field stations and crop varieties from Russia Federation or regions close to it). We marked each stage with an increasing ordinal number (k , from 1 to 5). For each phase, we regressed linear Developmental Rate function (Dr) as shown in eq. (1) using ordinary least squares technique (Fig. S1). Table 2 reports: *i*) the parameters (a , b) and the error ε of the linear regression; *ii*) base temperature T_0 and the related GDD; *iii*) the p-value and the linear correlation coefficient between developmental rates and average air temperature. Correlation analyses were carried through Pearson's product-moment method using a Student's t distribution for computing the p-value; Pearson correlation analyses always reject the null hypothesis of no correlation between developmental rates and temperature with high confidence (Table 2). Residuals from the linear model reveal that the correlations are unbiased and almost homoskedastic.

2.2 Stressful hot and frost extreme events

Stressful extreme events were defined as the occurrence of at least three consecutive days of maximum or minimum air temperature above and below, respectively, thresholds temperatures selected from a literature survey and mainly related to wheat key physiological damages.

Critical plant temperatures for damage showed large variability between published works (Porter and Gawith, 1999; Barlow et al., 2015), probably due to both differences in the experimental designs and for the genetic variability among crop varieties. However, averages for critical temperatures defining lethal limits and sterility response for wheat were relatively consistent. Key physiological damage to wheat in response to a selected frost event included seedling death,

sterility, and death of formed grains (Barlow et al 2015, Porter and Gawith, 1999; Bonciarelli and Bonciarelli, 1992). Since winter precipitation in most parts of the Russian Federation usually falls as snow with persistent duration (Groisman et al., 1994; Brown and Mote, 2009), thresholds for minimum temperatures we selected hypothesize adequate snow cover. Similarly, key physiological damage to wheat in response to a heat event included sterility and abortion of grains around anthesis and leaf senescence. Selected threshold temperatures, relative reference, and phenological stages are reported in [Table 3](#).

2.3 Sowing date

We had no spatial data on sowing dates over Russia Federation, but rather a general knowledge that winter grain sowing campaign begins in mid-August in the Volga Valley and advances southward, up to end in early November in the North Caucasus District (USDA, 2013). A well-established general rule suggests that colder the temperature regime the earlier occur the optimal planting period (Sacks et al., 2010), at least where the main limiting factor for crop development is winter stiffness. Published data on sowing dates from the agro-meteorological network of stations of Russia (Savin et al., 2007) confirmed this general trends but also revealed that sowing dates may differ from year to year up to 60 days due to the inter-annual climate variability.

Assuming that in Russian Federation the sowing date is mainly determined by cold temperature, a sowing date ([Figure S2](#)) suitable for our screening (hereinafter *suggested sowing date*) could be estimated such as to bring together the phase of beginning of tillering with the typical coldest day of the year, in order to give plants enough time to develop adequate root and top growth before the greatest winter stress (Bonciarelli and Bonciarelli, 1992). Hence, through a 30-years climatological analysis we estimated the typical coldest day of the winter and traced back to the suggested sowing date (further details in Sec. 2.6).

2.4 Climate dataset: ERA-Interim and CMIP5-ESMs

The input data used to implement our screening process are daily average (T_{ave}), maximum (T_{max}) and minimum (T_{min}) air temperature from the ERA-Interim dataset and five bias-corrected Earth System Models (ESMs) participating to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5). Data sources and references are summarized in Table 1.

ERA-Interim is a global atmospheric database storing reanalysis of meteorological forecast model and data assimilation system from 1979 to date, produced and continuously updated in real time by the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECWMF). Data have a regular spatial resolution of $0.75^\circ \times 0.75^\circ$ degree (WGS84 geoid) and cover all the globe.

The ERA-Interim simulations (1979-2016) were included in the historical analysis for evaluating consistency between CMIP5-ESM results and the current benchmark.

CMIP5-ESM bias-corrected outputs were available from data archives of the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis Intercomparison (PCMDI). At the time of writing, we were able to download five bias-corrected CMIP5-ESMs outputs (Tab. 1). Data have a regular spatial resolution of 0.5 degrees and embrace the period 1950-2005 (historical) and 2006-2099 under the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) scenarios adopted by the IPCC for its fifth Assessment Report (AR5) in 2014 (Van Vuuren et al., 2011). To our analyses, we selected the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios (i.e. radiative values forcing of +4.5 and +8.5 W/m² in the year 2100 relative to pre-industrial values).

2.5. Spatial scale and time frames

Analysis from CMIP5-ESMs and ERA-Interim were based on 0.5 and 0.75 degrees, respectively, consistently with the native data sources. The past trend of thermal suitability was analyzed over the period 1951-2016 considering both the CMIP5-ESMs outputs and the ERA-Interim.

Future scenarios were carried out through the CMIP5-ESMs outputs considering two time frames of approximately 30 years: near future (2021-2051) and far future (2071-2099), to be compared with the reference time frame 1971-2001 (hereinafter baseline).

2.6. Screening implementation

Overall, we tested annually where wheat heat requirement (Sec 2.1), counted from an estimated sowing date (Sec 2.3), would be satisfied without the occurrences of stressful frost and heat extreme events (Sec 2.2). Where such conditions were met, the running year was defined as thermally suitable for wheat development and further investigations were carried out. To do this, for each climate dataset (CMIP5-ESMs and ERA-Interim) falling into the geographic boundaries of Russian Federation, we implemented a three-steps approach:

2.6.1. Estimate the coldest days of the winter (*Jm*)

The typical coldest day of the winter was selected by the median of the annual coldest days over the time frame. Figure S3 gives an example for the baseline (1971-2000), considering the GFDL-ESM2M model and a random cell grid.

2.6.2 Track back to the suggested sowing date (*Js*) date

Starting from J_m we counted backward the heat requirement needed from sowing to the beginning of tillering (i.e. GDD above T_0 in $k(1)$ and $k(2)$, see Table 1) up to trace back to J_s . Heat requirement was counted using the daily average (median) air temperature of the time frame (red lines in the upper panel of Figure S2).

2.6.3 Screening the annual thermal suitability

We considered a sowing window of 10 days around J_s . Year by year, we check where the whole wheat heat requirement (from sowing to maturity) counted from the suggested sowing window was met within 330 days without occurrences of stressful extreme events (Table S3). When such conditions were met (from all the days of the sowing window), the running year was defined as *thermally suitable* and further investigations were carried out. We chose 330 days as a reasonable compromise between the additional time needed from wax maturity to reach physiological maturity (when harvest occurs) and the maximum length for a crop to grow in northern latitude (one year).

2.7. Ensemble analysis

Taking into account the large variability between different ESMs outputs, we used a simple yet informative ensemble median to aggregate the results on thermal suitability obtained from single CMIP5-ESMs, quantify the patterns of projected changes and show the results. Variability in the results was expressed by the ensemble interquartile range.

2.8. Statistical test.

Two statistical tests were applied to the results: Mann-Kendall (Mann 1945, Kendall 1975, Gilbert 1987) and the Mann-Whitney U tests (Mann and Whitney, 1947). The first allows assessing if there is a monotonic increase or decrease in a given time series (in our case, the data plotted in Fig. 1 of the main text), regardless of whether the trend was linear or not. The null hypothesis for this test was the absence of a trend in the time series. The Mann-Kendall test has the advantage respect to the simple linear regression that it does not have to be checked for normality of residuals, constant variance, and linearity of the relationship.

The Mann-Whitney U test allows pairwise comparisons between single scenarios of thermal suitability. The null hypothesis was that the central tendency of a given scenario is not significantly different from the others.

2.9. Ancillary dataset.

Average annual wheat production and harvested area for Russian Federation were taken from the Agribusiness Expert-Analytical Center (Rukhovich and Shapovalov, 2015) and the Agrospeaker Agency, respectively (Shamaev, 2014). Data of wheat harvested area from the Agrospeaker Agency were consistent with those reported by FAOSTAT (FAO, 2017) and have the advantage of distinguishing between winter and spring wheat habit.

We also used the Global MODIS (MCD12Q1) Land Cover (Type 1, 2006, version 005) product (Friedl et al., 2002) to filter the results and quantify the thermal suitability occurring only over the current land use types of croplands, cropland/natural vegetation mosaics and grasslands (broadly recalled in the text as croplands plus grasslands). Modis land cover product is available at http://webmap.ornl.gov/ogcdownload/dataset.jsp?ds_id=10004) with several customizable options (e.g. resolution, spatial extent).

RESULTS

Observed trends in wheat expansion

In the middle of the 20th century, about 2.5-3% (~45 Mha) of the whole Russian extension (~ 17·10⁶ Km²) was thermally suitable for wheat cultivation (Fig. 1a). This fraction was almost constant up to the late seventies, although accompanied by large variability between CMIP5-ESMs (ca. ±20 Mha, Fig. 1). After approximately 1980, results from both ERA-Interim and the CMIP5-ESM ensemble median showed a progressive increase of thermal suitability ($p<0.01$) accompanied by unvaried but still large variability (±20 Mha) among CMIP5-ESMs. As first order approximation, the growing trend has allowed a gain of about 10 Mha per decade of potential suitable cropland/grassland areas.

Figures 1b-c show the recent trends in Russian wheat yield and harvested area. Average yield increased significantly ($p<0.01$) from approximately 1.5 to 2.3 tons per hectare after 1990. Winter wheat harvested area (Fig. 1c) had a slight but significant increase over the last decade (~4Mha for the period 2005-2015, $p<0.01$), likely at the expense of spring wheat which harvested area decreased of approximately 2Mha ($p<0.01$).

Past and projected geographical distributions

The maps of Figure 2a shows the spatial distribution of thermal suitability obtained from the CMIP5-ESMs ensemble median for three time frames: baseline (1971-2000), near future (2021-2050) and far future (2071-2099). In the projected geographical distributions the thermal suitability was integrated as a probabilistic index (0-1) expressing the number of years over the time frame

where the thermal suitability was met. Figures 2 shows also the individual contributions (also expressed as probability index) to the thermal suitability of heat and frost extreme events (2b-c) and heat fulfillment (2d).

In the baseline, the probabilistic index for thermal suitability was very high (0.75-1) in the North Caucasus and part of the South Region, high (0.50-0.75) in the rest of the South Region and part of the Central Region, low to moderate (0-0.50) toward the north-eastern regions, and nil over the 65°N and in the eastern Siberia. A spot of high and very high probability index (i.e. 0.50-1) was also present in the Far East. Extreme frost events (Fig. 2b) during the vegetative phase and low heat resources (Fig. 2d) were the major limiting factors to the thermal suitability toward the north-eastern regions of Russia.

Projected thermal suitability foresees an increase and shift of thermal suitability toward the north-western regions and in the Far East (i.e. Primorsky Krai), due to the increase of heat resources (2d) accompanied by a decrease of extreme frost events (Fig 2b) during the vegetative phase. In all scenarios, regions thermically unsuitable for wheat development in baseline changed from low to moderate suitable (100-170 Mha) and from high to very high suitable (3-5 Mha). Nevertheless, in the southern regions, the increase of stressful heat events after heading (Fig. 2c) reduced the very high probability index (0.75-1) of thermal suitability emerged in the baseline, especially in the far future projections, despite the plentiful heat supply that characterized these areas (Fig. 2d).

Projected changes in total amounts

The balance between shifts across classes of probability is reported in Figure 3. Low to high (0-0.75) classes of probability index of thermal suitability increased with respect to the baseline across all the scenarios (average net gain of ca. 47 Mha), whilst very high probability decreased in three out of four scenarios (average net losses of 13Mha). However, the variability in the results obtained from different CMIP5-ESMs resulted large, especially in the very high range of probability (0.75-1) where in three out of four of the scenarios the variability (error-bars) in the results obtained from different CMIP5-ESMs waere larger than the ensemble median (bars).

In Figure 4, probability density functions show the 30-years variability of the suitable land area for single scenarios. All the scenarios projected a significant increase ($p < 0.01$) of suitable area with respect to the baseline, whilst no significant differences were found between scenarios themselves ($p < 0.01$). Box plots in Figure 4 provide a synthetic evaluation of total projected suitable land: projected increase of suitable land (difference from the baseline, median value) ranged from

approximately 18Mha (2021-205, RCP 4.5) to 32 Mha (2071-2099, RCP 4.5), while the variability (interquartile range) remained large and almost constant around 30Mha.

DISCUSSION

In the present work, we provided an examination of the past-to-future thermal suitability for winter wheat over Russian Federation to better understand how the increasing warming is affecting the country's wheat sector, and in turns, discuss some adaptation strategies.

Our findings showed an increase in thermal suitability over the past thirty years, acting as a fair wind for the current bloom of Russian wheat exports. For instance, an increase in thermal availability allows the switch from spring wheat (or from other spring cereal crops requiring less thermal supply) to winter wheat, the latter providing higher yield (Olmstead and Rhode, 2011). Indeed, we observe a transition to the winter wheat at the expense of spring wheat (approximately 2Mha, Fig. 1c) suggesting that the agriculture sector is already taking benefit from the warmer conditions, albeit a potential for wheat cultivation might still be unexploited: we estimated that in the recent past (1980-2010) additional 10 Mha per decade of agricultural land has become suitable for winter wheat due to more favorable thermal conditions. It's worthwhile recalling that about 40 Mha of arable land were estimated to be abandoned in Russia after the collapse of the former Soviet Union (Ioffe and Nefedova, 2004; Schierhorn et al., 2013), nowadays providing a remarkable and relatively sustainable resource of suitable agricultural land (Schierhorn et al., 2014). We can estimate a realistic yet cautionary gain in wheat production from the observed increase of thermal suitability (~30Mha for the period 1980-2010) embracing the European Russia (Fig 2a, baseline) where the abandoned lands are mostly found (Schierhorn et al., 2014). Assuming to recover 30Mha of abandoned lands for wheat production and to achieve a low average wheat yield (~ 1.5 t ha⁻¹, see Fig. 1b), a gain of approximately 45 Mt per year could be returned, more than Russia exported in 2016. However, our assumption need to be extremely cautionary. Land abandonment occurred both in the most fertile regions (the Central Chernozem and North Caucasus) where the major trouble for agriculture is the inadequate summer rains (Alcamo et al., 2007), and in the temperate European Russia where the physical environment is harsher (but there is water availability) and the share of grain production is lower (Ioffe and Nefedova; 2004 Schiernon et al., 2014). Hence, the recovery of abandoned lands may require different degree of efforts and investments, depending both on the characteristic of the physical environment and the degree of lands marginality (e.g. distance from a regional center and market infrastructures, Ioffe and Nefedova, 2004). Only a deep cost-benefit analysis that considers the better available solutions to increase the agricultural efficiency (i.e.

energy, nutrient and water use efficiency) could reveal whether and where it is overall sustainable to recover such abandoned lands, here beyond the scope of our research.

Our findings showed also *i*) a future increase in thermal suitability toward the north-western regions and in the Far East, with a potential additional area of approximately 18-32 Mha (2051-2050, RCP4.5). *ii*) an increasing risk of heat extreme events in the southern regions, which currently represent the most productive and intensively managed wheat cultivation areas.

The scenarios embracing the north-western regions were in agreement with previous works (Alcamo et al., 2007; Sirotenko et al., 2007; Zabel et al., 2014; Ramankutty et al., 2002). In these regions, extreme frost events (Fig. 2*b*) during the vegetative phase and low heat resources (Fig. 2*d*) were the major limiting factors for an high thermal suitability. Similarly, in the Far East the major limiting factor resulted the inadequate heat availability. Moreover, results suggested that regions thermically unsuitable for wheat development in baseline would change from low to moderate thermal suitability and, in small part, also from high to very high thermal suitability.

Overall, the current transition toward more suitable thermal conditions for winter wheat can be already exploited by means of different solutions, assuming that positive costs/benefits opportunities exist: planting spring wheat; planting other cereals than wheat that require less heat supply (e.g. barley (Poehlman, 1985)) or that are more resistant to very cold temperature (e.g. rye, which cold resistance allows autumn sowing also where the climate is prohibitively for the other cereal crops (Bonciarelli and Bonciarelli, 1992)); identify new suitable wheat varieties by means of crop breeding (Morran et al., 2011). From this point of view, investments aimed at research for new varieties can play a decisive role to face the climate changes. Moreover, improvements in crop genetics could probably increase also the potential yields (Tester and Langridge, 2010).

The projected increasing risk in the southern regions, in agreement with (Dronin and Kirilenko, 2011, Teixeira et al., 2013; Asseng et al., 2015), calls for urgent investment in adaptation strategies to preserve the currently most important wheat production basin (Asseng, 2014; Teixeira et al., 2013). Moreover, regions can become drier under warmer temperatures, as already documented for the southern Russia (Dronin and Kirilenko, 2011). Possible adaptation strategies could be: use crop varieties that are more resistant to higher temperature and/or more dry conditions (Mitra, 2001); identify the sowing period that minimize the risks between winter frost and summer heat stress; good water and land management practices aimed at increasing the irrigation efficiency (e.g. drip irrigation, curtailing off-field evaporative losses from water storage and transport; reducing on-field losses through mulching and reduced tillage).

Lastly, we have to point out that the thermal suitability we proposed does not account for the potential productivity but rather whether the characteristics of the climate are adequate for winter wheat development in terms of heat supply and risk of extreme events, based on a sowing date we suggested to overcome the winter stiff. Moreover, where the thermal suitability would met, then the screening of further variables (e.g. soil quality, water availability, etc) could improve the assessment to define a comprehensive land suitability.

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Author contributions

A.D.P and R.V. conceived and planned the study; A.D.P., L.C. and F.D.P. performed the calculation and statistical analysis; A.D.P and L.C. analyzed the results. I.V., O.N. and S.C. contributed to valuable criticism on Russian economy and agriculture. A.D.P, R.V., and L.C. wrote the paper.

Additional Information

Competing financial interests: the authors have no competing interests as defined by Nature Publishing Group, or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Wheat developmental rates (from Podolsky, 1984) used to estimate the base temperatures and related growing degree days for five wheat subphases. k = phase id (see Table S1); N = number of observations; R^2 = coefficient of determination; Black line: Developmental Rate Function (Dr), dotted lines $Dr \pm \epsilon$ (one standard deviation). Residuals (not shown) suggested no bias relations.

Figure S2. Suggested sowing dates (CMIP5-ESMs ensemble median) for winter wheat estimated such as to bring together the phase of beginning of tillering with the typical coldest day of the year.

Figure S3: example of climatological analysis carried out from the GFDL-ESM2M over the baseline (1971-2000) from a random cell grid (id=553) to compute the suggested sowing date, J_s . **Upper panel:** daily average air temperatures (blues line), their median (red line) and coldest days of the year (red asterisks), **Bottom panel:** boxplot of the coldest days. The median (red line of the boxplot) was selected to identify the typical coldest day of the year (J_m).

TABLES

Table 1. Climate dataset

Data source	Institution	period	Reference
ERA-Interim	European Center for Medium-Range Forecast	1979-2016	Dee 2011
CMIP5-GCMs:		2050-2099	
GFDL-ESM3M	Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory, USA		Donner et al. 2011
HadGEM2-ES	Met Office Hadley Centre, UK		Jones et al. 2011
IPSL-CM5A-MR	Institu Pierre-Somni Laplace, France		Dufresne et al. 2013
MIROC-ESM	AORI, NIES, JAMSTEC, Japan		Watanabe et al. 2011
NorESM1-M	Norwegian Climate Centre, Norway		Bentsen et al. 2013

Table 2. Dr functions calibrated with the phenological observations of Podolsky (1984). k = phase id; T_0 = base temperature, i.e. the temperature below which the plant development is supposed to be null; GDD = growing degree day or heat requirement: a and b = parameters of the linear regression; R^2 = coefficient of determination (i.e. the square Pearson coefficient); ε = error variable of the linear regression, used to track back the uncertainty on the base temperature; p = p-value of the linear correlation hypothesis.

Phases	k	T_0 [°C]	$Dr = a + b \cdot T + \varepsilon$			R^2	ε [d ⁻¹]	p
			GDD [°Cd]	a [d ⁻¹]	b [°C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹]			
Sowing - full mass sprouting	1	1,3±2.7	165	-0,0069	0,0061	0.52	0.016	0.1 10 ⁻⁶
Full mass sprouting – beginning of tillering	2	1.2±2.8	183	-0.0069	0.0055	0.61	0.0153	0.1 10 ⁻⁷
Beginning of Tillering – full stalk shooting	3	2,9±2.2	283	-0,0103	0,0035	0.70	0.007	0.7 10 ⁻⁷
Full Stalk Shooting - Heading	4	12.7±2.2	96	-0,1318	0,0104	0.46	0.0233	0.4 10 ⁻⁶
Heading – Wax Ripeness	5	7.5±2.2	446	-0,0169	0,0022	0.48	0.005	0.1 10 ⁻¹³

Table 3. Threshold of maximum and minimum air temperature used to identify stressful events. See Sec. 2 of SI for further details

Phase id (k)	Threshold for Max. temperature [°C]	Threshold for Min. temperature [°C]	Reference
1	--	-17°	Barlow et al., 2015 Porter and Gawith, 1999
2	--	-17°	Barlow et al., 2015 Porter and Gawith, 1999
3	--	-29° (with snow)	Barlow et al., 2015 Bonciarelli and Bonciarelli, 1992
4	--	-4°	Barlow et al., 2015
5	33°	-4°	Barlow et al., 2015

FIGURES

Figure 1. Thermal suitability (total amount of croplands plus grasslands) for wheat cultivation over Russian Federation (a), wheat average yield (b) and harvested area (c), recent trends. The lines in the left panel report a 9-years moving average of thermal suitability embracing only croplands and grasslands (according to MODIS land cover 2006 (Friedl et al., 2002)). Black dotted line: result obtained from CMIP5-ESMs ensemble median (gray shadow as interquartile); yellow-dotted line: result from ERA-Interim dataset; Average yields (not available for single spring and winter habit) and harvested area from the AB-Center (Rukhovich and Shapovalov, 2015) and Agrospeaker Agency (Shamaev, 2014).

Figure 2. Projected thermal suitability, and stressful frost and hot extreme events (expressed as probability indices over the time frame), CMIP5-ESMs ensemble median. Stressful extreme events were defined as the occurrence of at least three consecutive days of maximum or minimum air temperatures above and below, respectively, thresholds temperatures reported in Table S2.

Figure 3. Net projected changes of thermal suitability between classes of probability, CMIP5-ESMs ensemble median (bars as half of the interquartile range).

Figure 4. Probability density functions and boxplot showing the 30-years variability of the thermal suitability (total amount) for single scenarios. In each box, the central line is the median, the edges of the box are the 25th and 75th percentiles, the whiskers extend to the 10th and 90th percentile.

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